

Double neutrosophic integrals

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Abstract: Several previous papers dealt with neutrosophic integrals without introducing the idea of double neutrosophic integrals. In this article, double integrals were discussed by presenting several theories in double neutrosophic integrals over a rectangle and over a general region, the most important of which is the neutrosophic Fubini's theorem. In addition to studying the applications of double neutrosophic integrals in calculating areas.

Keywords: neutrosophic integrals, double neutrosophic integrals, neutrosophic Fubini's theorem, area.

1. Introduction

In contrast to the current logics, Smarandache suggested the Neutrosophic Logic to describe a mathematical model of uncertainty, vagueness, ambiguity, imprecision, undefined, unknown, incompleteness, inconsistency, redundancy, and contradiction. Smarandache introduced the concept of neutrosophy as a new school of philosophy [4]. He presented the definition of the standard form of neutrosophic real number [3-5], studying the concept of the Neutrosophic probability [6], the Neutrosophic statistics [5-7], and professor Smarandache entered the concept of preliminary calculus of the differential and integral calculus, where he introduced for the first time the notions of neutrosophic mereo-limit, mereo-continuity, mereoderivative, and mereo-integral [1]. A number of studies in the area of integration and differentiation were given by Y. Alhasan [9-12-15], also he presented the definition of the concept of neutrosophic complex numbers and its properties, in addition, he studied the general exponential form of a neutrosophic complex number [2-10]. Madeleine Al- Taha presented results on single valued neutrosophic (weak) polygroups [13]. The AH isometry was used to study many structures such as conic sections, real analysis concepts, and geometrical surfaces [11-16].

The calculation of area, volume, and arc length is one of the most essential uses of integration in human life. In our reality, there are things that cannot be precisely defined and contain an element of indeterminacy.

There are four sections of paper. first section, which includes a study of neutrosophic science, serves as an introduction. The second portion deals with a neutrosophic integrals theories and rules. The double neutrosophic integral and its applications are discussed in the third part. The fourth section offers the paper's conclusion.

2. Preliminaries

2.1. Neutrosophic integration by substitution method [15]

Definition 1

Let $f: D_f \subseteq R \rightarrow R_f \cup \{I\}$, to evaluate $\int f(x)dx$

put: $x = g(u) \Rightarrow dx = g'(u)du$

by substitution, we get:

$$\int f(x)dx = \int f(u)g'(u)du$$

Definition 3.2[16]

Let $f: R(I) \rightarrow R(I)$; $f = f(X)$ and $X = x + yI \in R(I)$ then f is called a neutrosophic real function with one neutrosophic variable. a neutrosophic real function $f(X)$ written as follows:

$$f(X) = f(x + yI) = f(x) + I[f(x + y) - f(x)]$$

3. Double neutrosophic integrals over a rectangle

Theorem 2 (neutrosophic Fubini's theorem)

Let $f(x, y, I)$ integrable over the rectangle

$R \cup I = \{(x, y, I): \dot{a} + \dot{a}_0I \leq x \leq \dot{b} + \dot{b}_0I \text{ and } \dot{c} + \dot{c}_0I \leq y \leq \dot{d} + \dot{d}_0I\}$, where:

$\dot{a}, \dot{a}_0, \dot{b}, \dot{b}_0, \dot{c}, \dot{c}_0, \dot{d}, \dot{d}_0$ are real numbers, while $I =$ indeterminacy.

Then we can write the double neutrosophic integrals over a rectangle $R \cup I$ by the following formula:

$$\iint_{R \cup I} f(x, y, I) dA = \int_{\dot{a} + \dot{a}_0I}^{\dot{b} + \dot{b}_0I} \int_{\dot{c} + \dot{c}_0I}^{\dot{d} + \dot{d}_0I} f(x, y, I) dydx = \int_{\dot{c} + \dot{c}_0I}^{\dot{d} + \dot{d}_0I} \int_{\dot{a} + \dot{a}_0I}^{\dot{b} + \dot{b}_0I} f(x, y, I) dx dy$$

Integration according to the horizontal slice:

$$\int_{\dot{c} + \dot{c}_0I}^{\dot{d} + \dot{d}_0I} \int_{\dot{a} + \dot{a}_0I}^{\dot{b} + \dot{b}_0I} f(x, y, I) dx dy$$

Integration according to the vertical slice:

$$\int_{\dot{a} + \dot{a}_0I}^{\dot{b} + \dot{b}_0I} \int_{\dot{c} + \dot{c}_0I}^{\dot{d} + \dot{d}_0I} f(x, y, I) dy dx$$

Example 1

Let $R \cup I = \{(x, y, I): 0 \leq x \leq 2 + 2I \text{ and } 1 + I \leq y \leq 4 + 4I\}$, then let find:

$$\iint_{R \cup I} (x^2 + 2Ixy) dA$$

Solution:

Integration according to the vertical slice:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_0^{2+2I} \int_{1+I}^{4+4I} (x^2 + 2Ixy) dy dx = \int_0^{2+2I} (x^2y + Ixy^2) \Big|_{1+I}^{4+4I} dx \\
 &= \int_0^{2+2I} ([(4+4I)x^2 + Ix(4+4I)^2] - [(1+I)x^2 + Ix(1+I)^2]) dx \\
 &= \int_0^{2+2I} [(3+3I)x^2 + 60Ix] dx = ((1+I)x^3 + 30Ix^2) \Big|_0^{2+2I} \\
 &= (1+I)(2+2I)^3 + 30I(2+2I)^2 \\
 &= (1+I)(8+56I) + 480I \\
 &= 8 + 56I + 8I + 56I + 480I = \boxed{8 + 600I}
 \end{aligned}$$

Integration according to the horizontal slice:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_{1+I}^{4+4I} \int_0^{2+2I} (x^2 + 2Ixy) dx dy = \int_{1+I}^{4+4I} \left(\frac{x^3}{3} + Ix^2y \right) \Big|_0^{2+2I} dy \\
 &= \int_{1+I}^{4+4I} \left(\left[\left(\frac{(2+2I)^3}{3} + I(2+2I)^2y \right) \right] - [0] \right) dy \\
 &= \int_{1+I}^{4+4I} \left(\frac{(8+56I)}{3} + 16Iy \right) dy \\
 &= \left(\frac{(8+56I)}{3}y + 8Iy^2 \right) \Big|_{1+I}^{4+4I} \\
 &= \left[\frac{(8+56I)}{3}(4+4I) + 8I(4+4I)^2 \right] - \left[\frac{(8+56I)}{3}(1+I) + 8Iy(1+I)^2 \right] \\
 &= (1+I)[(8+56I) + 296I] \\
 &= (1+I)(8+296I) \\
 &= 8 + 296I + 296I + 8I = \boxed{8 + 600I}
 \end{aligned}$$

note that we got the same result.

3.1 Double neutrosophic integrals over a general region

Theorem 3

Let $f(x, y, I)$ is continuous on the region

$R \cup I = \{(x, y, I): \dot{a} + \dot{a}_0 I \leq x \leq \dot{b} + \dot{b}_0 I \text{ and } g_1(x, I) \leq y \leq g_2(x, I)\}$, where: $\dot{a}, \dot{a}_0, \dot{b}, \dot{b}_0$ are real numbers, while $I =$ indeterminacy, and $g_1(x, I), g_2(x, I)$ continuous neutrosophic functions, where $g_1(x, I) \leq g_2(x, I)$, for all $x \in [\dot{a} + \dot{a}_0 I, \dot{b} + \dot{b}_0 I]$.

Then we can write the double neutrosophic integrals a general region $R \cup I$ by the following formula:

$$\iint_{R \cup I} f(x, y, I) dA = \int_{\dot{a} + \dot{a}_0 I}^{\dot{b} + \dot{b}_0 I} \int_{g_1(x, I)}^{g_2(x, I)} f(x, y, I) dy dx$$

Example 2

Let $R \cup I = \{(x, y, I): 0 \leq x \leq 4 + 4I \text{ and } 0 \leq y \leq (1 + I)x\}$, then let find:

$$\iint_{R \cup I} (2e^{x^2} - \sin y) dA$$

Solution:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{4+4I} \int_0^{(1+I)x} (2e^{x^2} - \sin y) dy dx &= \int_0^{4+4I} (2ye^{x^2} + \cos y) \Big|_0^{(1+I)x} dx \\ &= \int_0^{4+4I} ([2(1+I)xe^{x^2} + \cos(1+I)x] - [0 + \cos 0]) dx \\ &= \int_0^{4+4I} ([2(1+I)xe^{x^2} + \cos(1+I)x] - [1]) dx \\ &= \left((1+I)e^{x^2} + \frac{1}{1+I} \sin(1+I)x - x \right) \Big|_0^{4+4I} \\ &= \left[(1+I)e^{(4+4I)^2} + \frac{1}{1+I} \sin(1+I)(4+4I) - 4 - 4I \right] - \left[(1+I)e^0 + \frac{1}{1+I} \sin(0) - 0 \right] \\ &= (1+I)e^{(4+4I)^2} + \frac{1}{1+I} \sin(1+I)(4+4I) - 4 - 4I - 1 - I \\ &= (1+I)e^{16+48I} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}I \right) \sin(4+12I) - 5 - 5I \\ &= (1+I)(e^{16} + I[e^{64} - e^{16}]) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}I \right) (\sin(4) + I[\sin(16) - \sin(4)]) - 5 - 5I \end{aligned}$$

Example 2

Let $R \cup I = \{(x, y, I): 0 \leq x \leq 1 + I \text{ and } 0 \leq y \leq x\}$, then let find:

$$\iint_{R \cup I} \frac{\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}I\right)x}{x} dA$$

Solution:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \iint_{ROI} \frac{\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}I\right)x}{x} dA &= \int_0^{1+I} \int_0^x \frac{\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}I\right)x}{x} dy dx \\
 &= \int_0^{1+I} \frac{\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}I\right)x}{x} y \Big|_0^x dx \\
 &= \int_0^{1+I} \left(\left[\frac{\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}I\right)x}{x} x \right] - \left[\frac{\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}I\right)x}{x} (0) \right] \right) dx \\
 &= \int_0^{1+I} \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}I\right)x dx \\
 &= \frac{-1}{\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}I\right)x \Big|_0^{1+I} \\
 &= \left[\frac{-1}{\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}I\right)(1+I) \right] - \left[\frac{-1}{\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}I\right)(0) \right] \\
 &= \left[\frac{-1}{\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}I\right)(1+I) \right] - \left[\frac{-1}{\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4}} \right] \\
 &= \left[\left(\frac{-3}{\pi} + \frac{9}{7\pi}I\right) \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{5\pi}{6}I\right) \right] - \left[\frac{-3}{\pi} + \frac{9}{7\pi}I \right] \\
 &= \left(\frac{-3}{\pi} + \frac{9}{7\pi}I\right) \left[\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) + I \left[\cos\left(\frac{7\pi}{6}\right) - \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) \right] \right] - \left[\frac{-3}{\pi} + \frac{9}{7\pi}I \right] \\
 &= \left(\frac{-3}{\pi} + \frac{9}{7\pi}I\right) \left[\frac{1}{2} + I \left[\frac{-\sqrt{3}}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \right] \right] - \left[\frac{-3}{\pi} + \frac{9}{7\pi}I \right] \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{-3}{\pi} + \frac{9}{7\pi}I\right) + I \left(\frac{-\sqrt{3}}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\right) \left(\frac{-3}{\pi} + \frac{9}{7\pi}I\right) - \left(\frac{-3}{\pi} + \frac{9}{7\pi}I\right) \\
 &= \frac{-1}{2} \left(\frac{-3}{\pi} + \frac{9}{7\pi}I\right) + I \left(\frac{-\sqrt{3}}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\right) \left(\frac{-3}{\pi} + \frac{9}{7\pi}I\right) \\
 &= \frac{3}{2\pi} - \frac{9}{14\pi}I + \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2\pi}I - \frac{9\sqrt{3}}{14\pi}I + \frac{3}{2\pi}I - \frac{9}{14\pi}I \\
 &= \frac{3}{2\pi} + \left(\frac{3 + 12\sqrt{3}}{14\pi}\right)I
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 3

$$\int_0^{1+\frac{1}{2}I} \int_0^x x \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I\right) y \, dy \, dx$$

$$= \int_0^{1+\frac{1}{2}I} \frac{-1}{\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I} x \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I\right) y \Big|_0^x \, dx$$

$$= \int_0^{1+\frac{1}{2}I} \left(\left[\frac{-1}{\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I} x \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I\right) y \right] - \left[\frac{-1}{\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I} x \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I\right) (0) \right] \right) dx$$

$$= \int_0^{1+\frac{1}{2}I} \left(\left[\left(\frac{-3}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\pi}I\right) x \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I\right) x \right] - \left[\frac{-3}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\pi}I \right] x \right) dx$$

derivation	integration
(+) $\left(\frac{-3}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\pi}I\right) x$	$\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I\right) x$
(-) $\left(\frac{-3}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\pi}I\right)$	$\left(\frac{-3}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\pi}I\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I\right) x$
0	$\left(\frac{-3}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\pi}I\right)^2 \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I\right) x$

$$= \left(\left[\left(\frac{-3}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\pi}I\right)^2 x \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I\right) x - \left(\frac{-3}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\pi}I\right)^3 \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I\right) x \right] - \left[\frac{-3}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\pi}I \right] \frac{x^2}{2} \right) \Big|_0^{1+\frac{1}{2}I}$$

$$= \left(\left[\left(\frac{-3}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\pi}I\right)^2 \left(1 + \frac{1}{2}I\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{2}I\right) - \left(\frac{-3}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\pi}I\right)^3 \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{6}I\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{2}I\right) \right] \right. \\ \left. - \left[\frac{-3}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\pi}I \right] \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{2}I\right)^2}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{-3}{\pi} - \frac{1}{\pi}I\right)^3$$

$$= \left(\left[\left(\frac{9}{\pi^2} - \frac{3}{\pi^2}I\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{7\pi}{12}I\right) - \left(\frac{27}{\pi^3} + \frac{29}{\pi^3}I\right) \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{7\pi}{12}I\right) \right] - \left[\frac{-3}{2\pi} - \frac{3}{4\pi}I \right] - \left(\frac{27}{\pi^3} + \frac{29}{\pi^3}I\right) \right)$$

$$= \left(\frac{9}{\pi^2} - \frac{3}{\pi^2}I\right) \left(\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) + I \left[\sin\left(\frac{11\pi}{12}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right)\right]\right) - \left(\frac{27}{\pi^3} + \frac{29}{\pi^3}I\right) \left(\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) + I \left[\cos\left(\frac{11\pi}{12}\right) - \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right)\right]\right) \\ + \frac{3}{2\pi} + \frac{3}{4\pi}I - \left(\frac{27}{\pi^3} + \frac{29}{\pi^3}I\right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left(\frac{9}{\pi^2} - \frac{3}{\pi^2}I\right) \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} + I \left[\frac{\sqrt{6} - \sqrt{2} - \sqrt{3}}{4}\right]\right) - \left(\frac{27}{\pi^3} + \frac{29}{\pi^3}I\right) \left(\frac{1}{2} + I \left[\frac{-\sqrt{6} - \sqrt{2} - 1}{4}\right]\right) + \frac{3}{2\pi} + \frac{3}{4\pi}I \\
 &\quad - \left(\frac{27}{\pi^3} + \frac{29}{\pi^3}I\right) \\
 &= \left(\frac{9}{\pi^2} - \frac{3}{\pi^2}I\right) \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{6} - \sqrt{2} - 2\sqrt{3}}{4}I\right) - \left(\frac{27}{\pi^3} + \frac{29}{\pi^3}I\right) \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{-\sqrt{6} - \sqrt{2} - 2}{4}I\right) + \frac{3}{2\pi} + \frac{3}{4\pi}I \\
 &\quad - \left(\frac{27}{\pi^3} + \frac{29}{\pi^3}I\right) \\
 &= \left(\frac{9}{\pi^2} - \frac{3}{\pi^2}I\right) \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{6} - \sqrt{2} - 2\sqrt{3}}{4}I\right) - \left(\frac{27}{\pi^3} + \frac{29}{\pi^3}I\right) \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{-\sqrt{6} - \sqrt{2} - 2}{4}I\right) + \frac{3}{2\pi} + \frac{3}{4\pi}I \\
 &\quad - \left(\frac{27}{\pi^3} + \frac{29}{\pi^3}I\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4

Let $f(x, y, I)$ is continuous on the region

$R \cup I = \{(x, y, I): \dot{c} + \dot{c}_0I \leq y \leq \dot{d} + \dot{d}_0I \text{ and } h_1(y, I) \leq x \leq h_2(y, I)\}$, where: $\dot{c}, \dot{c}_0, \dot{d}, \dot{d}_0$ are real numbers, while $I =$ indeterminacy, and $h_1(y, I), h_2(y, I)$ continuous neutrosophic functions, where $h_1(y, I) \leq h_2(y, I)$, for all $y \in [\dot{c} + \dot{c}_0I, \dot{d} + \dot{d}_0I]$.

Then we can write the double neutrosophic integrals a general region $R \cup I$ by the following formula:

$$\iint_{R \cup I} f(x, y, I) \, dA = \int_{\dot{c} + \dot{c}_0I}^{\dot{d} + \dot{d}_0I} \int_{h_1(y, I)}^{h_2(y, I)} f(x, y, I) \, dx dy$$

Example 4

Let $R \cup I = \{(x, y, I): 1 + I \leq y \leq 3 + 3I \text{ and } (1 + I)y \leq x \leq y^2\}$, then let find:

$$\iint_{R \cup I} 5 \, dA$$

Solution:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\int_{1+I}^{3+3I} \int_{(1+I)y}^{y^2} 5 \, dx dy = \int_{1+I}^{3+3I} 5x|_{(1+I)y}^{y^2} \, dy \\
 &= 5 \int_{1+I}^{3+3I} (y^2 - (1+I)y) \, dy \\
 &= 5 \left(\frac{y^3}{3} - (1+I)\frac{y^2}{2} \right) \Big|_{1+I}^{3+3I} \\
 &= 5 \left(\left[\frac{(3+3I)^3}{3} - (1+I)\frac{(3+3I)^2}{2} \right] - \left[\frac{(1+I)^3}{3} - (1+I)\frac{(1+I)^2}{2} \right] \right) \\
 &= 5 \left(\left[\frac{9(1+I)^3}{2} \right] - \left[\frac{(1+I)^3}{6} \right] \right) = \frac{65(1+I)^3}{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{65(1 + 7I)}{3} = \frac{65}{3} + \frac{455}{3}$$

Theorem 5

Let $f(x, y, I)$ and $g(x, y, I)$ be integrable over region $R \cup I \subset \mathbb{R}^2$, and let $\dot{c} + \dot{c}_0 I$ any constant, where \dot{c}, \dot{c}_0 are real numbers, while $I =$ indeterminacy. Then:

$$(i) \iint_{R \cup I} (\dot{c} + \dot{c}_0 I) f(x, y, I) \, dA = (\dot{c} + \dot{c}_0 I) \iint_{R \cup I} f(x, y, I) \, dA$$

$$(ii) \iint_{R \cup I} [f(x, y, I) + g(x, y, I)] \, dA = \iint_{R \cup I} f(x, y, I) \, dA + \iint_{R \cup I} g(x, y, I) \, dA$$

(iii) If $R \cup I = R_1 \cup R_2 \cup I$, where R_1, R_2 are nonoverlapping region, then:

$$\iint_{R \cup I} f(x, y, I) \, dA = \iint_{R_1} f(x, y, I) \, dA + \iint_{R_2} f(x, y, I) \, dA$$

3.2 Applications of double neutrosophic integrals

The area of region t can be calculated using a double neutrosophic integrals:

$$A = \iint_{R \cup I} dx dy = \iint_{R \cup I} dy dx$$

Example 5

Using a double neutrosophic integrals to find the area of the plane region bounded by the curve of $y = x^2$ and $y = (1 + I)x$.

Solution:

Let find the intersection points of the two equations:

$$x^2 = (1 + I)x$$

$$x^2 - (1 + I)x = 0$$

$$x(x - 1 - I) = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \begin{cases} x = 0 \\ x = 1 + I \end{cases}$$

$$\Rightarrow \quad \begin{cases} y = 0 \\ y = 1 + 3I \end{cases}$$

so, the two equations intersect at the points: $(0, 0)$ and $(1 + I, 1 + 3I)$

➤ Integration according to the horizontal slice:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{1+I} \int_{x^2}^{(1+I)x} dy dx &= \int_0^{1+I} y \Big|_{x^2}^{(1+I)x} dx \\ &= \int_0^{1+I} ((1 + I)x - x^2) dx \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \left((1+I) \frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{x^3}{3} \right) \Big|_0^{1+I} \\
&= (1+I) \frac{(1+I)^2}{2} - \frac{(1+I)^3}{3} \\
&= \frac{(1+I)^3}{6} = \boxed{\frac{1}{6} + \frac{7}{6}I}
\end{aligned}$$

➤ Integration according to the vertical slice:

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_0^{1+3I} \int_{(1-\frac{1}{2}I)y}^{\sqrt{y}} dx dy &= \int_0^{1+3I} x \Big|_{(1-\frac{1}{2}I)y}^{\sqrt{y}} dx \\
&= \int_0^{1+3I} \left(\sqrt{y} - (1-\frac{1}{2}I)y \right) dy \\
&= \left(\frac{2}{3} \sqrt{y^3} - (1-\frac{1}{2}I) \frac{y^2}{2} \right) \Big|_0^{1+3I} \\
&= \left[\frac{2}{3} \sqrt{(1+3I)^3} - (1-\frac{1}{2}I) \frac{(1+3I)^2}{2} \right] - \left[\frac{2}{3} \sqrt{0^3} - (1-\frac{1}{2}I) \frac{0^2}{2} \right] \\
&= \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{1+63I} - (1-\frac{1}{2}I) \frac{(1+15I)}{2} \\
&= \frac{2}{3} (1+7I) - \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{15}{2}I - \frac{1}{4}I - \frac{15}{4}I \right) \\
&= \frac{2}{3} (1+7I) - \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{7}{2}I \right) \\
&= \frac{2}{3} + \frac{14I}{3} - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{7}{2}I = \boxed{\frac{1}{6} + \frac{7}{6}I}
\end{aligned}$$

note that we got the same result.

Example 6

Using a double neutrosophic integrals to find the area of the plane region bounded by the curve of $y = 9 + 7I - x^2$ and x - axis.

Solution:

$$9 + 7I - x^2 = 0$$

$$x^2 = 9 + 7I$$

by root the both sides, we get on:

$$\Rightarrow \begin{cases} x = 3 + I \\ x = -3 - I \end{cases} \quad (1) \quad \text{or} \quad \begin{cases} x = 3 - 7I \\ x = -3 + 7I \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where:

$$\sqrt{9 + 7I} = \gamma + \delta I$$

$$9 + 7I = \gamma^2 + 2\gamma\delta I + \delta^2 I$$

$$9 + 7I = \gamma^2 + (2\gamma\delta + \delta^2)I$$

then:

$$\begin{cases} \gamma^2 = 9 \\ 2\gamma\delta + \delta^2 = 7 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} \gamma = \pm 3 \\ \delta^2 + 2\gamma\delta - 7 = 0 \end{cases}$$

find the values of β :

$$\text{➤ When } \gamma = 3 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \delta^2 + 6\delta - 7 = 0$$

$$(\delta + 7)(\delta - 1) = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \delta = -7, \delta = 1$$

$$\text{➤ When } \gamma = -3 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \delta^2 - 6\delta - 7 = 0$$

$$(\delta - 7)(\delta + 1) = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \delta = 7, \delta = -1$$

$$\sqrt{9 + 7I} = 3 + I$$

$$\text{or} \quad = -3 - I$$

$$\text{or} \quad = 3 - 7I$$

$$\text{or} \quad = -3 + 7I$$

case (1):

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \int_{-3-I}^{3+I} \int_0^{9+7I-x^2} dy dx = \int_{-3-I}^{3+I} y|_0^{9+7I-x^2} dx \\ &= \int_{-3-I}^{3+I} (9 + 7I - x^2) dx \\ &= \left((9 + 7I)x - \frac{x^3}{3} \right) \Big|_{-3-I}^{3+I} \\ &= \left[(9 + 7I)(3 + I) - \frac{(3 + I)^3}{3} \right] - \left[(9 + 7I)(-3 - I) - \frac{(-3 - I)^3}{3} \right] \\ &= 2 \left[(9 + 7I)(3 + I) - \frac{(3 + I)^3}{3} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$= 2 \left[27 + 37I - \left(\frac{27 + 27I + 9I + I}{3} \right) \right]$$

$$= 2 \left[27 + 37I - 9 - \frac{37I}{3} \right] = 36 + \frac{148}{3}I$$

case (2):

$$A = \int_{-3+7I}^{3-7I} \int_0^{9+7I-x^2} dy dx = \int_{-3+7I}^{3-7I} y|_0^{9+7I-x^2} dx$$

$$= \int_{-3+7I}^{3-7I} (9 + 7I - x^2) dx$$

$$= \left((9 + 7I)x - \frac{x^3}{3} \right) \Big|_{-3+7I}^{3-7I}$$

$$= \left[(9 + 7I)(3 - 7I) - \frac{(3 - 7I)^3}{3} \right] - \left[(9 + 7I)(-3 + 7I) - \frac{(-3 + 7I)^3}{3} \right]$$

$$= \left[(9 + 7I)(3 - 7I) - \frac{(3 - 7I)^3}{3} \right] + \left[(9 + 7I)(3 - 7I) - \frac{(3 - 7I)^3}{3} \right]$$

$$= 2 \left[(9 + 7I)(3 - 7I) - \frac{(3 - 7I)^3}{3} \right]$$

$$= 2 \left[27 - 91I - \left(\frac{27 - 189I + 441I - 343I}{3} \right) \right]$$

$$= 2 \left[27 + 91I - 9 + \frac{91I}{3} \right] = 36 + \frac{364}{3}I$$

4. Conclusions

The significance of this paper stems from the fact that it explained the concept of double neutrosophic integrals. where double neutrosophic integrals over a rectangle and over a general region were presented. In addition, integrations were calculated according to the horizontal and vertical slice, and we got the same results in both cases. Also, we introduced the applications of double neutrosophic integrals.

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